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What Factors Influence the Increasing Dependency on Mobile Banking in Bangladesh - A Quantitative Study

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ABSTRACT

Mobile Banking is a groundbreaking innovation yet new and surging sector that is expanding rapidly in Bangladesh. Financial service providers have introduced this pioneering innovation. It's important to understand what factors may play a vital role for individuals to use mobile banking in Bangladesh; however, the related research is still limited. The study aims to identify influential factors of Bangladesh's rapidly growing M-banking sectors. A quantitative study based on a survey was adopted with 200 mobile banking users in Dhaka city was selected as participants for the scientific study. The statistical analysis method using SPSS software initiated the result. Participants think a wide variety of m-banking features with easy access and availability plays a significant role in surging the system. The Covid-19 pandemic has also increased people's dependency on m-banking. Apart from that, m-banking authorities have no direct contact with its customers. More safety, the large number of money transactions, prohibiting money laundering and simple deposit and profit limit features and reduced charges are all factors that would attract more customers in the coming days.

Keywords

Mobile financial services, mobile banking, financial technology, banking technology, financial inclusion, bkaash, rocket, nagad, mfss user's attitude, influential factors, quantitative study, m-banking.

Introduction

Mobile Banking is a relatively new concept in Bangladesh. Technological developments help enhance the performance of banks' distribution channels, and developments in the banking industry that employ electronic delivery channels are referred to as electronic banking. Electronic commerce is currently believed to hold the potential of a new business revolution by providing a low-cost and direct means of exchanging information and selling or buying goods and services. Changes in distribution channels have fueled the growth of banking technology, as shown by ATMs, phone banking, telebanking, PC banking, and, most recently, internet banking.

Before 2000, there was no financing system through mobile phones. At that time, the number of mobile users was significantly limited. Dutch Bangla Bank introduced the first-ever mobile banking (hereinafter, m-banking) services in Bangladesh on March 31, 2011. Bangladesh is a densely populated country with 160 million people yet few bank accounts. Most of them used to rely on unreliable and slow money transfer systems to send and receive money, using Middleman. Within just one decade, Mobile banking in Bangladesh has changed the concept of Banking.

M-banking services data by Bangladesh Bank, which is the central bank of Bangladesh, suggest that, in 2021, 15 Banks will be providing m-banking services in Bangladesh with the amount of 71,246.88 crore BDT. The number of registered clients is 995.88 lac, [1 lac = 0.10 million and 1 crore = 10 million] as of May 2021. Money Banking services have successfully engaged people from different income sources, classes, etc. Currently, in Bangladesh, "Bkash" is the leading m-banking service. According to BRAC Bank, "BRAC Bank's subsidiary, bKash Limited, takes financial services to 30 million people providing money transfer, transactional and micro-saving services with its presence in every village of the country". Bill Gates said that, "Banking is more fundamental than I realized. There have been attempts: microfinance groups, Co-operatives, but the transaction fees have always been too high. Until we get those services down the very low fees onto the cellphone in digital mode only then banking will always be for those who are better off." (Shams, 2016) "Terminologically, m-banking is known as mobile financial services in Bangladesh" (Azad, 2016). M-banking services bring unbanked people under the umbrella of financing services. "M-banking can be defined as a channel whereby the customer interacts with a bank via a mobile device, such as a mobile phone or personal digital assistant (PDA)." (Barnes & Corbitt, 2003). Wikipedia defines M-banking as "Mobile banking is a service provided by a bank or other financial institution that allows its customers to conduct financial transactions remotely using a mobile device such as a smartphone or tablet." (Mobile Banking, 2019, P1). Bangladesh Bank has defined Mobile Financial Services as "Mobile Financial Services (MFS) is an approach to offering financial services that combines banking with mobile wireless networks that enable users to execute banking transactions." (Nabi et al., 2012). So MFS stands for banking activity without going to the bank branches. The mobile financial services market is still in its initial stages, with suppliers trying to stabilize their systems, create agent networks, and gain new clients. This includes recruiting and training agents, marketing, assisting customers with transactions, and gaining customers via know-your-customer (KYC) and account opening processes. According to a study done by Bangladesh's central bank, the new services are reaching many country regions, and most consumers and agents are cautiously optimistic about the value of mobile financial services.

"In Bangladesh, MFS got popular in the name of Mobile Banking. Generally, the agents of respective banks enable these services after registering the mobile account. Under this platform, a mobile account owner can withdraw cash and send/receive money via the independent agent locations without visiting any bank." (Tabassum, 2021). In other words, M-banking enables the opportunity to make deposits, withdraw, send or receive funds from mobile accounts to agent or one mobile accounts holder to others. Thus, it is possible to

make transactions in rural areas without going to the respective bank branches. Krishnan 2014 suggest that "A system like that wouldn't have required lots of infrastructure. A decent mobile network and a handful of mobile phones would have made a big difference in the lives of those poor people" (Krishnan, 2014). This concept of m-banking has changed the lives of people here, both in the business sector and daily life activities. Mobile banking is a new concept in Bangladesh that began on March 31, 2011. In Bangladesh, a number of banks have launched mobile banking services. Previously, the central bank allowed mobile financial services such as inbound international remittances, cash in/out via m-wallets, private to private (P2P), business to private (B2P), government to private (G2P), and many more.

"There are around 151.82 million people in Bangladesh according to (adb.org/bangladesh), 2012 of which only 13 percent have bank accounts whereas more than 95 percent are mobile phone users." (Information on Mobile Banking. n.d.). Bangladesh's economy is agriculture-based. According to the World Bank (2015), 65.72 percent of the entire population lives in rural areas, and agriculture is their primary economic activity. However, it is difficult for banks to build branches or ATMs in all of Bangladesh's rural areas. As a result, many people, although requiring financial services, cannot obtain them. This is one of the primary reasons mobile banking was brought into the market to address this demand.

"Furthermore, by the end of January 2016, the total number of mobile phone subscribers had reached a level. Furthermore, by the end of January 2016, mobile phone subscribers had reached approximately 132 million (BTRC website). As a result, the moment had come to launch the innovative mobile banking system in the Bangladeshi market.

In Bangladesh, M-banking Services has started with only money transactions. With time, now this service is not confined the just transaction. M-banking offers a wide range of services, including online payments, paying utility bills, interest on savings, easy-to-use smartphone applications (both in English and Native Language), transfer money from abroad, etc. are remarkable and popular services. Now 15 banks have been involved in providing m-banking services. The following table below attempts to show popular m-banking services with their parent organization.

SN.	Mobile Banking Name	Parents Organization	Inauguration Date
01	Bkash	BRAC Bank Ltd	July 2011
02	Rocket (DBBL)	Dutch Bangla Bank Ltd	May 2011*

03	Nagad	Bangladesh Post Office, Ministry of Post and Telecommunication (Bangladesh)	March 26 2019
04	Rupali Bank Sure Cash	Rupali Bank	December 2014
05	M-Cash	Islami Bank Bangladesh Ltd	August 2012
06	Upay	United Commercial Bank Ltd. Bangladesh	November 2013
07	Ok Mobile	One Bank Limited	October 2013
08	My Cash	Mercantile Bank Limited	February 2012
09	Trust Axiata Banking	Trust Bank Ltd & Axiata Digital	April 1 2018

*= First-ever m-banking services in Bangladesh.

Due to the rapid emergence and success of Mobile Financial Services (MFSs), many people in Bangladesh have become aware of their importance. However, the industry is not yet in a stable position. Despite being a new system in Bangladesh, as shown in the table, Never been introduced before the 2010s, MFS users and popularity have been increasing daily. "According to Fortune, 22% of Bangladeshi adults use bKash with around 4.5 million daily transactions" (bKash, 2021, P. 2b). Despite the barriers, the number of mobile banking users is still enormous. "Transactions of internet banking amounted to Tk10,371.1 crore in March this year, up 57.42% year-on-year, according to the latest data from the Bangladesh Bank" (Hasan, 2021). In Bangladesh, the number of clients enlisted for portable managing an account increment quickly after the nation lockdown, which began on 26th Walk 2020 in Bangladesh. In January 2020, the enlisted versatile keeping money clients were 80.92 million, which was risen strongly to 92.57 million in July. Inside the following five sequential months, the number steadily expanded to 99.34 million in December 2020. This development rate was higher than the going before the year 2019. In truth, the rate was begun to extend more strongly after June 2020 than the same time of the past year due to the announcement of the Government and other originations to send/receive cash through portable keeping money.

The study aims to determine the factors behind the increasing dependency on m-banking. Few findings in this study are similar to past research, but others are different and new in this field of knowledge.

1.1 Background of the study

The past study relating to M-banking/ Mobile Banking services have mainly focused on the impact of MFSs on rural life, MFSs infrastructure deficits, concepts, prospects and problems MFSs in Bangladesh, people access and customers' attitude to MFSs (Ahmed et al., 2011; Hossain & Haque, 2014; Islam et al., 2017; Islam & Salma, 2016; Khatun et al., 2021). Shahanur, 2013 discusses that traditional banking is costlier than mobile banking and more time-consuming, whereas a study of Sohel 2021 found that every respondent believes m-banking is speedy. However, past studies have shown some valuable information about the MFSs situation in Bangladesh. And have shown notable gaps in this field of study. "Limited access to financial services is considered an important bottleneck for curbing poverty in Bangladesh. Digital technology such as mobile banking can contribute to accelerate people's access to finance but did not receive proper attention before COVID-19." (Khatun et al., 2021). But it cannot draw a relation between customers' income sources and their opinion about using MFSs during the Covid-19 pandemic concerning the study's research question.

1.2 Research Objectives & Questions

This study explores the factors, relationships, and types of income sources people attached to m-banking. It develops a clear and broad idea of this increasing m-banking sector in Bangladesh.

1. What are the reasons behind the superfluous increase in mobile banking in Bangladesh?
2. What sort of economic class people is using mobile banking more?
3. What types of relationships between mobile banking authorities and users are fostering online banking in Bangladesh?

M-banking is widely used throughout Bangladesh regardless of people with literacy or without literacy. Due to Covid-19, the whole country has faced trouble in every sector, yet m-banking has been surging day by day. In the following chapters, their literature review from various articles, book chapters, or journals; methodology of this study, Data Analysis from the statistical analysis, discussion and relation between diverse literature and data.

1.3 Research Framework

2 Literature Review

2.1 The benefits of Mobile banking

"Mobile banking is a global behavioral phenomenon, or more accurately, it is the result of significant behavioral changes that have been occurring all over the world since the introduction of the Internet and the World Wide Web." (Krishnan, 2014). Due to the emergence of m-banking, banking users can now conduct transactions anywhere and at any time. "According to Mustafa K Mujeri, executive director of the Institute for Inclusive Finance and Development, about 33% of the total population of Bangladesh has no access to formal banking service or any micro-financial institution. In this situation, MFS appeared as a boon for the rural unbanked people in Bangladesh. MFS has successfully brought around five crores, unbanked Bangladeshi people, under formal financial services in the last few years" (Tabassum, 2021). Traditional banking has a significant role in the financial system, but it has failed to financial inclusion in Bangladesh. Traditional banking needs physical activity such as physical presence, customer's presence at the bank, banking hour transactions, holidays, and paper works to complete a transaction.

On the other hand, m-banking has surpassed all these issues. Krishnan 2014 describes this banking revolution as "Mobile banking takes the location requirement out of banking. This is a critical concept, this notion that mobile technology renders your location largely irrelevant. With mobile banking, you never have to find a branch. All you have to do is find your phone!" (Krishnan, 2014). Once you have registered for your account, the use of paperwork is no more. A customer can transact money from anywhere at any time. Most m-banking offers 24 hours service. A person can access his account round the clock and do all the procedures with the touch of few simple buttons. One important thing to mention, M-banking had a limited amount transaction limit in Bangladesh. During the Covid-19 lockdown, BB authorities have raised the limit for the welfare of people. "It has raised the monthly transaction limit to Tk 2 lakh from Tk 75,000 and omitted the fees for transactions up to Tk 40,000. However, it has set the highest limit for each transaction at Tk 10,000." (BB raises mobile, 2021). For financial inclusion, M-banking has been playing a vital role. It enables the opportunity to bring everyone under the umbrella of financial services. The arrival of technology such as the internet, mobile phones, etc m-banking has reduced paper-based activities and made life easier. "There are around 151.82 million people in Bangladesh as of 2012; only 13 percent of them have bank accounts. But more than 95 percent of people in Bangladesh use mobile phones. Banks can now offer banking services to both the rural community and the wider population (without banking transactions) through mobile phones. Day by day, this service will become more popular in Bangladesh. Through it, it is possible to take money easily to remote areas. Small transactions are become very easy through mobile banking. Not only in rural areas, but also in urban areas these transactions are equally popular" (Sultana, 2019).

M-banking offers money transactions and other services at a meager cost. One reason is that m-banking doesn't need any physical branches and human resources, so m-banking services charge less than traditional banking. Barnes and Corbitt 2003 describe, "Some of the first commercial applications of the mobile internet involve wireless or mobile (m-) banking. These developments build on earlier ideas of customer channel extension

through telephone banking and online banking. M-banking taps the mobile customer channel in an effort to further reduce costs" (Barnes & Corbitt, 2003).

M-banking is a safer and more secure method of conducting banking transactions. It has various security features that make it faster and less prone to fraudulent transactions. Another advantage of m-banking is that poor and underprivileged customers widely use it. Mobile banking is more favorable to rural populations in Bangladesh, such as farmers and local people in business. The complications of money transactions have been eliminated by enrolling in mobile banking. Going to the bank is tough for rural residents because the nearest one is many miles distant.

Nevertheless, mobile banking is convenient for them. They may quickly and effectively and simply receive and send money using a mobile phone or visit the nearest agent in the local market. It doesn't matter if the village inhabitants dropped out of school at a young age and could not read or write. They can transfer money using a cell phone instead of filling out forms in writing. It simplifies their lives. The traditional bank does not exist in every location. Sending and receiving money has never been easier. But how can individuals believe agents? Is there a problem with insecurity? The solution resides in the character of the society in which the general population of Bangladesh lives and the interpersonal ties we cultivate. A villager who goes to an agent, for example, is a fellow villager, maybe someone he has known for many years or is even related to. Alternatively, you can commit your money to the 'parar mudir dokan,' who also serves as an agent in the city. In these situations, there is generally no lack of trust. The agents are a part of the people, deeply embedded of the community members. Money could also be received from outside the country.

"Mobile financial services can be divided into m-banking and mobile payment..." (Ahmed et al., 2012). There is a new addition to m-banking in money-saving. Customer can save their money and, based on their amount, can also get interest. Unbanked people can easily save money by using m-banking. M-banking is very popular in Bangladesh as it seems to grow rapidly. Tabassum 2021 explains the interest rate of Bkash as follows "For example, if an individual (bKash account owner) keeps a minimum balance of BDT 1,000 in his/her bKash account throughout a month, does at least 2 transactions, and keeps an average day end balance between BDT 1,000 to BDT 5,000.99 in that month. Then, that individual (bKash account owner) will receive 1.5% rate of interest (at an annual rate) upon the average balance of that specific month"(Tabassum, 2021). Like Bkash, other MFSs in Bangladesh have also provided this service to their customers.

2.2 Mobile banking in developed countries

Most of the MFS services have been bought up through agent banking. "An agent is a third party owner of an outlet who conducts banking transactions such as cash deposits, withdrawals, small value loan disbursement and recovery of loans, transfer of funds, paying bills under the government's social safety net programs, and

account inquiries on behalf of a bank" (Islam, 2018). An agent is a third party owner who conducts banking transactions at their risk. Lack of proper security for agents is a major constraint. Another drawback of this rapidly growing sector is fraud people. When a customer withdraws money from an agent, fraud people try to steal their money or call that customer to get his pin code. "The Cyber and Special Crime Division of the Detective Branch (DB) of police has arrested nine alleged members of a gang engaged in defrauding money using mobile financial service app bKash...Then they called the clients over the phone and told them that their bKash account had been cloned and they would soon get a call from the customer care" (Javed, 2020). As the m-banking authority provides guidelines both for agents and its customers, these fraudulent activities cannot be solved without the awareness and safety concerns of the customers and agents. As a result of the study, Hossain & Haque, 2014 emphasizes "Security of financial transactions, being executed from some remote location and transmission of financial information over the air, is the most complicated challenge that needs to be addressed jointly by mobile application developers, wireless network service providers and the banks IT departments" (Hossain & Haque, 2014).

M-banking services largely depend on the internet. Customers can use the services through USSD and smartphone applications. "USSD (Unstructured Supplementary Service Data) is a Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM) protocol that is used to send text messages. USSD is similar to Short Message Service (SMS)." (Rosencrance, 2020). From a simple bar phone customer use m-banking through ussd option. Hossain and Haque 2014 also highlighted the use of the sms function in m-banking: "Moreover, the communication between the bank and the customer will be carried out via text messages. The messages may triggered automatically by the bank whenever certain predefined events occurred, for example, whenever a transaction is performed on the account"(Hossain & Haque, 2014). According to Bangladesh Bank statistics, the overall number of agents at the start of 2013 was 60,000. By the end of February 2015, the figure had risen to more over 540,000. This significant differential illustrates the space's fast expansion in a relatively short period of time. Because the majority of agents in Bangladesh are not exclusive, many of them represent several suppliers. The overall number of agents is derived using statistics obtained from individual suppliers and aggregated by Bangladesh Bank. As a result of duplicate and triple counting, the real number of agents is likely to be substantially lower than the stated figure. For example, if the typical agent offers services to three providers, as predicted by CGAP, the total number of unique agents would be just 180,000.

In smartphones, customers use applications from respective banking services. For this, they need a stable internet connection. Internet connection speed is an issue in Bangladesh. "Bangladesh has stepped down further behind in terms of mobile internet speed, ranking 135th out of 137 countries." (Bangladesh ranked 135th, 2021). The report further added, "The country is only ahead of Afghanistan and Venezuela in the list, according to the June report of Ookla, a global platform that works with the speed and comparative picture of the internet." Ahmed et al, 2011 also discusses the drawbacks "In Bangladesh, the expansion of e-banking is beset with several infrastructural, institutional, and regulatory constraints such as inadequate availability of

reliable and secure telecommunication infrastructure, absence of a backbone network connecting the whole country, poor ICT penetration in the banking sector, lack of skilled manpower and training facilities, absence of supportive policies, guidelines, rules and regulations relating to e-transactions and the like". M-banking banking authorities have nothing to do with this aspect as mobile network coverages and internet speeds is regulated by other ministry of Bangladesh. But it affects primarily m-banking. "Describing his sufferings after availing the mobile number portability service, Sayed Nazrul Islam, a telecom subscriber from Chattogram, said that the technical difficulty in receiving his bank transaction related SMS after availing the MNP service had forced him to return to his previous operator." ([Mobile users aggrieved, n.d.](#)). Despite the fact that mobile phone penetration is high in Bangladesh, a huge percentage of the population still utilizes mobile phones just to make and receive phone calls. When it comes to MFS, it may be regarded as more technical, and because it involves money, it may be viewed as hazardous. Using an agent is a method of transferring the risk to a professional. Because some users may be hesitant to complete a transaction on their own, utilizing an agent alleviates their apprehension about using this technology. To conduct transactions, almost all MFS providers provide an English-only USSD menu. As a result, those who lack the requisite level of literacy to understand English to complete a transaction on their own frequently choose to use OTC. The Bangladesh Bank has published a circular to discourage mobile payments made by those who do not have a mobile wallet. However, they have yet to develop a method for adequately monitoring agents and taking appropriate response. For example, because providers do not have access to the national ID database, it is not yet feasible to detect a fraudulent customer. MFS transactions are time-sensitive and must be performed as soon as possible. Agents will not give cash to a consumer until they have received an SMS confirming that the transaction was successful. Inability to complete a transaction can also demotivate clients who are trying it for the first time, leading to bad views. Because the transaction platform is the foundation upon which everything else is built, it is critical to select the proper technology from the start. The transaction platform operates in the background and provides functionality based on each bank's business model and strategy. Although the success of the service is determined by the business strategy and the bank's ability to execute it, selecting the improper platform might have a diverse effect.

2.3 Determinants of mobile banking usage

Covid-19 pandemic has forced everyone to stay in their houses. It poses both health and economic problems. People were forced to remain in their residence. They couldn't be able to make payments physically. The demands and uses of m-banking have increased drastically by this time. And people also realize the importance of m-banking as they can't move freely. The influence of m-banking can be understood properly by the statement of BB as published in BB raises money 2021 report states that "Bangladesh Bank today raised the person to person mobile banking transaction limit to help people transfer money with ease during the countrywide seven-day lockdown starting from tomorrow."

The Government of Bangladesh has announced fiscal stimulus packages for Small and Medium Enterprises, North American Academic Research, 5(3) | March 2022 | <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6399334> Monthly Journal by TWASP, USA | 247

Garment Sectors, daily workers and Low-income people. "The government is providing direct cash assistance to 5.0 million Corona-affected families." (Govt. Cash Gift, 2020). Further (Govt. Cash Gift, 2020) added that "Under this programme, Rupali Bank SureCash is directly disbursing Tk 2.0 billion to the mobile account among 8 hundred thousand beneficiaries. Recipients can withdraw the money at SureCash agent points around the country free of charge"(Govt. Cash Gift, 2020). To receive stimulus funds, one needs to have SureCash account. SureCash is a m-banking service provided by Rupali Bank. This decision of the Government has led people to use m-banking services as they couldn't roam freely during the lockdown.

"Traditional Banking services have failed to include major population in Bangladesh. Rural and underprivileged people are always left behind from traditional banking due to scarcity of capital, branch distances, failure to cope with the formal banking system etc. The key reasons for excluding a large number of people include lack of direct access to financial institutions and suitable products, high operational costs and risks arising from asymmetric information. Financial industry needs to find more cost effective ways to serve the unbanked poor with customized products." (Sultana & Khan, 2016) Whereas M-banking has succeeded in this aspect and created an equal opportunity for all. Moreover, numerous difficulties, such as a lack of an acceptable regulatory framework and mobile transaction security, tend to obstruct the continuing development of this advanced mobile banking application. Because of the concerns mentioned in this section and the relevance of mobile banking, research must be conducted to assess the possibilities and obstacles of mobile banking in a developing economy like Bangladesh.

Before introducing m-banking in Bangladesh, Rural and underprivileged people remained outside of the financial system. "This lack of access to finance in some parts of the developing world stifles entrepreneurship, stunts development and leaves people trapped in a poor, cash-only society". (Alexander, 2009 as cited in Sultana 2009)." Apart from those people, there is the inertia of people going to the bank and use banking services. Azad 2016, in his study shows that "Only 40% of adults nationwide had an account at a formal financial institution. Which gives the basic ground for the scope of m-banking". (Azad 2016)

Mobile phone adoption is one of the vital factors for this aspect. Today we now have more mobile phones than Personal computers in Bangladesh. "The total number of Mobile Phone subscribers has reached 171.854 Million at the end of January, 2021." (Mobile phone subscribers, 2021). With the advancement of mobile technology, the numbers of internet users and mobile network coverage in the last ten years have both increased significantly. "The total number of Internet Subscribers has reached 112.713 Million at the end of January, 2021" (BTRC, 2021). This advancement of technology use has created opportunities for all people to bring financial services under the umbrella. "However, the outstanding growth of mobile sector worldwide has created a unique opportunity to provide social and financial services over the mobile network. With over 4 billion mobile cellular subscriptions worldwide, mobile network has the ability to immediately offer mobile banking to 61% of the world population" (Sultana, 2009)

M-banking offers a wide variety of lucrative options and offers for its customers. Discounts on online payment, contactless payment during the lockdown, and discounts on various shops while you have to pay more on

physical payment, utility bills, etc, are both time and savings. "The following mobile banking services are currently offering in the country: (i) Disbursement of inward foreign remittances; (ii) Cash in/out using mobile account through agents/Bank branches/ATM's/Mobile Operator's outlets; (iii) Person to Business Payments (e.g. utility bills payment); (iv) Business to Person Payments (e.g. salary disbursement by corporate bodies/industries/offices etc); (v) Government to Person Payments (e.g. elderly allowances, freedom fighter allowances, subsidies, etc); (vi) Person to Government Payments e.g. tax, levy payments; (vii) Person to Person Payments (among registered account holders of the same bank) and (viii) Other payments like microfinance, overdrawn facility, insurance premium, DPS, etc" (Sultana and Khan, 2016 as cited in Khatun et al, 2021).

One important feature of m-banking which has helped rural people is Money transfer from abroad. 10 million citizens of Bangladesh work abroad as a migrants and short term employees which is very important for Bangladesh economy. Rural people mostly reluctant to go to the formal settings. Now with the help of m-banking money transfers, they can withdraw money nearby agents shop. This service enables these peoples to withdraw money any time and, most importantly, helps them improve their lives. Mobile Financial Services (MFS) comparative summary statement of May by BB 2021 shows that "inward remittance through banking of the month of May and June is 249.80 and 176.98 crore taka [1 lac = 0.10 million and 1 crore = 10 million]." The converted number of Taka in million is respectively 2498 million and 1769.8 million Bangladeshi Taka. This amount is not negligible in terms of low-income family members and underprivileged people. With m-banking, this feature is helping day by day to improve those people's lives. The multifaceted use of m-banking has been gaining popularity day by day. There is a scarcity of job sectors in Bangladesh. Many jobless people have been forced to move on freelancing, allowing them to work at home and get payment from abroad. This process has some limitations due to recognized money transfer platforms. To alleviate this situation, the central bank of Bangladesh has permitted money transfer through m-banking for freelance workers. On February, 2021 BB announced that "Bangladesh Bank today allowed mobile financial service (MFS) providers to bring remittance in order to facilitate freelance workers" (IT freelancers can, 2021). After the development of the COVID-19, the rate of increment of enlisted versatile keeping money clients from Walk to December 2020 was approximately 21 percent as against 16 percent amid the same period of the past year. Really, due to the COVID-19 widespread, individuals got to be anxious about transmission and favored to pay their extra installments such as power, gas, and other utility bills through computerized installment strategies. For this, an expansive number of modern versatile keeping money clients have risen amid this widespread circumstance. Presently, they utilize their portable keeping money stages and feel comfortable doing such exercises in this existing circumstance. Another vital truth behind rising portable managing an account client is that most of the readymade piece of clothing (RMG) proprietors requested their laborers to open a portable keeping money account to get their pay rates. And other motivations which could be a great activity to permit the moo workers into an advanced monetary get to stage in Bangladesh. This too, offers assistance to diminish the spread of COVID-19 within the nation.

Since its independence, the traditional bank has been functional in Bangladesh, yet it has failed to financial inclusion due to lack of physical presence everywhere. There are others factors too. Aside from that, m-banking with its agent banking can reach anyone at any place. The report by Islam,2018 suggests that "By the end of March this year, the number of agent banking accounts stood at 1,468,797 with deposits of Tk1,634.36 crore, according to the latest estimate of Bangladesh Bank". Agent banking does not confine themselves with just money transaction and withdrawal. It provides small loans to the people. Islam, 2018 further added, "...the banks have started giving out small loans through the outlets. As of March 31, this year, six banks have disbursed Tk122.25 crore in credit through their agent banking outlets." Globally, Bangladesh has become a success story for mobile phone-based financial services, with the industry lately witnessing a 186 percent increase in mobile financial transactions and a 262 percent increase in mobile banking customers. However, a substantial part of both urban and rural populations are still hesitant to embrace and use mobile banking services. As a result, there is a need to understand why consumers accept and utilize mobile banking and identify the variables that might influence their intents to use mobile banking in Bangladesh.

There are some remarkable research works about m-banking in Bangladesh. And this field of study is expanding rapidly. Yet online books on m-banking in Bangladesh are hard to find.

Materials and methods

3.1 Nature of study

The quantitative study is descriptive. The research design chosen for this scientific study is descriptive. "As the name implies, the major purpose of descriptive research is to describe characteristics of objects, people, groups, organizations, or environments. In other words, descriptive research tries to paint a picture of a given situation by addressing who, what, when, where, and how questions" (Zikmund et al., 2013).

As M-banking has been gaining popularity day by day, there is no need to conduct exploratory research. A descriptive design would help get insight into this phenomenon—a survey method employed to collect responses from the m-banking users. The study aims to locate the factors that influence increasing mobile banking in Bangladesh. A quantitative study will be employed to conduct the study. "Survey research designs are procedures in quantitative research in which investigators administer a survey to a sample or to the entire population of people to describe the attitudes, opinions, behaviors, or characteristics of the population" (Creswell, 2008, p.628). A survey method will be used, and data will be collected using a structured questionnaire. The study population is enormous. Therefore, cluster sampling will be used. This study will also explore the stakeholders' current scenario and key roles, which will eventually help identify the relationships among the users and online banking. A structured questionnaire will collect data from the population and analyzed to gain insight about this topic.

The table below attempt to pose a clear visual of the complete plan of the collecting data for the study:

Research Approach	Type of Data	Participant	Sample Size	Data Collection Method	Instrument
Quantitative	Primary	Online Mobile Banking Users.	200	Survey Structured Questionnaire	Opinionative

The table below attempt to pose a clear visual of the complete plan of the collecting data for the study:

Research Approach and type of data	Participant	Sample Size	Date Collection Method and Instrument
Quantitative & Primary	Online Mobile Banking Users from Dhanmondi Area, Dhaka.	200	Survey Structured Questionnaire

Structured Questionnaire was prepared and piloted among a group of m-banking users, which of them did not include in the final data collection phase. After the piloting phase, modifications of the Questionnaire were done, and confusing and double information was deleted.

Structured Questionnaire has two parts. The first part intends to gather responses about the participant's basic information, i.e., age, monthly income, m-bank service user, duration of usage of m-banking etc. The second part of the Questionnaire included 35 questions. These questions try to find the answer to this study's research question. These questions were selected to measure the respondent's opinions about the use of mobile banking. Later, data were analyzed using SPSS software. The descriptive analysis method was used. To illustrate the respondent's response, frequencies, charts, percentages were used.

3.2 Research Design

3.3 Credibility and Rigor

A structured questionnaire assured data credibility. On the other information, credibility was done by the participants and researcher. To ensure the credibility of the research various kinds of things have been kept in mind. Such as:

- **Research type:** Quantitative study.
- **Data collection credibility:** Data has been collected through a structured questionnaire.
- **Information credibility:** 200 participants have given information.
- **Analyst credibility:** To clarify the blur spots in the analysis process, seniors and peer researchers review the findings.

3.4 Population and sample

Dhanmondi area was selected for this study. Due to the global pandemic, a strict nationwide lockdown was imposed. As a result, it was impossible to collect data face to face or in person. Data was collected through mail or google form. Especially data was collected from the mobile banking users because of the convenience.

On the contrary, Clusters sampling was used to get valid information from the participants. It is also called geographical sampling. So it is hoped that the same sorts of responses would be collected from other locations with slight variation. The study aims to learn about influential factors of mobile banking users, precisely what they think about it.

In this quantitative study, the purpose is to find out the influential factors of mobile banking. For this, the participants of this study are usually MFS users. Cluster sampling, also known as geographical sampling, is considered for the study. Assuming MFSs users' response may vary slightly in another area as everywhere the services of MFS are the same. A Structured questionnaire has filled up by 200 active MFSs users from the different occupations in the Dhanmondi area.

3.5 Research participants

Inhabitants (Student, Businessman and Job holder) of Dhanmondi Area, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Two hundred (200) participants were chosen from the inhabitants of the Dhanmondi area, especially students and job holders, who relied on mobile banking.

3.6 Analysis technique

This study has followed the survey method. A structured questionnaire has been developed to get desired responses. Structured Questionnaire for quantitative data collection, only one tool was used to avail the data. Though it is quantitative research, it is a mainly descriptive one. For this analysis is based on description. After taking data from the participants, coding and recoding were used, and data were converted into code.

Unnecessary data was removed. Incredibly obscure and non-readable data is deleted through coding. On the other hand, the descriptive analysis function of SPSS was formulated to conduct the analysis, which will be described entirely in the later part.

3.7 Ethical issues

Research ethics is significant for a scientific study. Finishing a study with appropriate research guidelines, research ethics is essential. As it is a scientific study, the whole research is conducted and maintained strictly. Participants were spontaneous to share their views, and any influence was not imposed on them. The data was collected with their consent. Privacy and secrecy of their identity will be maintained properly.

In this study, respondents have enough time to give their true views on the research questions. Before collecting data, proper consent and permission was taken from the respondents. Most importantly, secondary source data from any sources are included with proper reference. Moreover all the step of research guideline was maintained.

3.8 Limitation

Because of the pandemic situation in person data was not possible to collect. The main limitation of this study is physical data collection. The whole time for data collection hindered by the Covid-19 pandemic lockdown in Bangladesh. Another limitation is an inability to remove biases from the responses. As MFS study is expanding rapidly in Bangladesh, academic books in Bangladesh are very limited.

4 Data Analysis

4.1 Background Information

The age of the respondents range from 17 to 70 years. Most of the respondents 74.8% are from 21-30 years. They are followed by those between 31-40 years (7.9%), 41-50 years 2.6%, 51-60 years (1.3%), under 20 years 12.6% and 61 and older (.7%). See table 1 for details.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Under 20	19	12.6	12.6	12.6
	21-30	113	74.8	74.8	87.4
	31-40	12	7.9	7.9	95.4
	41-50	4	2.6	2.6	98.0
	51-60	2	1.3	1.3	99.3
	61 and older	1	.7	.7	100.0
	Total	151	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey

Approximately one-third of the respondents are from 21-30 years age group. This age group is generally well-educated, mobile banking users and needs to go places for their job responsibilities. Most importantly, this group is economically sound and has mobile devices. For this reason, this group is perfect for this study as they are good with mobile device use and technology.

Table 2 shows that most of the respondents came from the student group (74.8%). The rest are Job holders (21.2%), businessmen (4%). For more details, please see table 2.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Businessman	6	4.0	4.0	4.0
	Job Holder	32	21.2	21.2	25.2
	Student	113	74.8	74.8	100.0
	Total	151	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey

This table implies a trend that students are most familiar and excessive users of mobile technology and m-banking. So, m-banking finance transactions are most popular among the student group, then Job Holder and the rest.

Table 3 shows that most respondents' monthly income range is 1000-10000 BDT [Bangladeshi Taka] (47.7%). Rest two big groups are 10001-20000 BDT (11.9%) and Under 1000 BDT (11.9%). For more details, please see table 3.

Table 3: Monthly Income of the respondents					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Under 1000	18	11.9	11.9	11.9
	1001-10000	72	47.7	47.7	59.6
	10001-20000	18	11.9	11.9	71.5
	20001-30000	9	6.0	6.0	77.5
	30001-40000	14	9.3	9.3	86.8
	40001-50000	10	6.6	6.6	93.4
	50001-60000	4	2.6	2.6	96.0
	60001 and older	6	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	151	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey

As most participants are from student groups, this table 3 implies that low-income group people use m-banking more.

When asked which mobile services they use, most of the response favors Bkash (44.4%) then following are Nagad (33%), Rocket (33%) and the rest are shown in table 4.

Table 4: Mobile Banking Services User					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Bkash	67	44.4	44.4	44.4
	Nagad	33	21.9	21.9	66.2
	Others	1	.7	.7	66.9
	Rocket	33	21.9	21.9	88.7
	T Cash	5	3.3	3.3	92.1
	Telecash	3	2.0	2.0	94.0
	U Pay	9	6.0	6.0	100.0
	Total	151	100.0	100.0	

As discussed earlier, Bkash is one of the MFS that revolutionized the m-banking sector in Bangladesh. After 17 months of operation, Bkash currently has 30,000 agents, nearly one in every two villages in rural Bangladesh, "ensuring access to agents in the country's most distant areas." On July 21, 2011, the service

became live. It presently has 2.2 million subscribers enrolled. Furthermore, Bkash is available to 98 percent of mobile subscribers in Bangladesh. Partnerships with the country's four main GSM providers enable this penetration level. This table also suggests that among MFSs users, Bkash is the most used m-banking service.

4.2 Data Analysis

	N	Range	Minimu m	Maximu m	Mean	Std. Deviation
Mobile banking services are much easier to use on bar phones.	151	5	0	5	3.34	1.624
Mobile banking services are much easier to use on smartphones.	151	5	0	5	4.23	.927
Mobile banking services-related applications are much easier to use.	151	5	0	5	3.99	1.017
Can you easily use mobile banking application?	151	5	0	5	3.63	1.258
Do you need the help of others to use mobile banking services?	151	5	0	5	1.94	1.775
Valid N (list wise)	151					

Source: Field Survey, Note 5 strongly agree, 4 Agree, 3 Somewhat Agree, 2 Somewhat Disagree, 1 Disagree, 0 Strongly Disagree.

Mean is very important on a six-point Likert scale. From 0.01 to 1.00 it means strongly disagree, from 1.01 to 2.00 it means disagree. From 2.01 to 3.00, it means somewhat agree, from 3.01 to 4.00 it means somewhat agree. From 4.01 to 5.00, it means agree; from 5.01 to 6.00 it means strongly agree.

When asked about mobile banking on bar phones, most participants slightly agree with the statements, whereas, on smartphones, the mean is 4.23. M-banking services are much easier on the smartphone rather than bar phones. When it comes to mobile banking applications, respondents gave their opinion affirmative. And for application use respondents can do that easily on their own. This result implies that respondents can operate m-banking smoothly through their mobile devices.

Table 6: Users opinion towards m-banking contrast with physical banking

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Mobile banking services have made my life easier.	151	0	5	4.05	1.076
I can use money transactions feature very easily through mobile banking services.	151	0	5	4.06	1.173
Mobile banking services allows me to transact money from anywhere.	151	0	5	3.85	1.315
The money transactions cost in mobile banking is cheaper.	150	0	5	2.95	1.496
For money transactions, I don't need to go to the bank.	151	0	5	3.54	1.295
I do large financial transactions in mobile banking services.	151	0	5	2.56	1.499
I do business transactions through mobile banking services.	151	0	5	2.93	1.429
Valid N (listwise)	150				

Source: Field Survey.

One of the basic differences between m-banking and the regular bank is the presence everywhere. When asked the respondents about this difference, m-banking gets a much higher opinion. Respondents in this study expressed that M-banking made their life easy (mean 4.05) and available money transaction facilities anytime (4.06 & 3.85). Respondents also said that they do not need to go to the physical bank (mean 3.54). But for large and financial transactions, they imply that respondents mainly rely on the physical banking system.

Table 7: Respondents opinion about Safety Concern in M-banking

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Mobile banking services are much safer.	149	0	5	3.19	1.250

I never had been deceived by using mobile banking services.	151	0	5	3.42	1.323
In Mobile banking services, there is a risk of fraud.	149	0	5	3.59	1.380
Valid N (list wise)	147				

Source: Field Survey.

When asked about the fraudulent activities in m-banking, respondents expressed that there's a good chance of being deceived in this concern (mean 3.59). When asked about the safety feature of m-banking respondents implies that this system is secure (mean 3, 19), but this safety should be upgraded more. Customers are unwilling to utilize mobile banking because they are concerned about data breaches over telecommunication networks. Apart from it, there are still issues about technological difficulty, conceptual gap, preference, knowledge gap, unwillingness, habit, and security threat and confidentiality concern.

Table 8: Respondents opinion about M-banking Features

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
I shop online through mobile banking services.	151	0	5	3.59	1.261
I pay electricity bills through mobile banking services.	151	0	5	3.18	1.545
I pay gas bills through mobile banking services.	151	0	5	2.99	1.629
I pay water bills through mobile banking services.	151	0	5	3.01	1.596
I recharge my mobile through mobile banking services.	150	0	5	3.87	1.249
Relatives send me money from abroad through mobile banking services.	151	0	5	3.13	1.459
Money can be sent abroad through mobile banking services.	151	0	5	3.05	1.382

The mobile banking application has attractive offers on financial transactions.	151	0	5	3.05	1.408
Valid N (listwise)	150				

Source: Field Survey

When respondents asked about the multifaceted features of m-banking, respondents expressed their opinion positively. Bill payments, mobile top-up, and sending money abroad are extraordinary features that attract more people to m-banking, saving time and money. For transactions, m-bank provides extra discounts, so people are encouraged to buy things through m-banking and draw online shopping (mean 3.05).

Table 9: Respondents opinion about the relation between users and M-banking authority

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
First time I learn about mobile banking services from bank.	151	0	5	2.74	1.610
First time I learn about mobile banking services from neighbors'.	151	0	5	3.42	1.303
Bank convinces me to use mobile banking services.	150	0	5	3.15	1.432
The mobile banking services authority always keeps in touch with me	151	0	5	2.44	1.586
I often go to mobile banking service office.	151	0	5	2.15	1.534
Valid N (listwise)	150				

Source: Field Survey.

This study tries to draw the relation between users and concerned m-banking authority. When asked where they first knew about M-banking, respondents expressed that they heard about it from their neighbor (mean 3.42) rather than from the concerned bank authority (mean 2.74). Bank has little connection with m-banking users (mean 2.44). Respondents also said they barely go to the m-banking physical offices (mean 2.15). M-banking is an agent-based service, or in some cases, users go to the atm booth for money withdrawal. For technical support, users contact customer calls support except for any serious issue; they go to the physical customer center.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Covid-19 pandemic have increased the dependency on mobile banking services.	151	0	5	3.56	1.340
Do you use mobile banking services before the outbreak of Covid-19 pandemic?	151	0	5	3.45	1.473
Do you start to use mobile banking services due to the outbreak of Covid-19?	151	0	5	2.18	1.693
Do you use mobile banking services due to Covid-19 incentive packages?	151	0	5	1.86	1.669
Valid N (listwise)	151				

Source: Field Survey.

The covid-19 pandemic has affected every aspect of our lives, including economic abilities. Respondents expressed increased dependency on M-banking for financial issues (Mean 3.56). But when asked the respondents do they use M-banking before or after the outbreak, respondents gave more emphasis on before the pandemic (mean 3.45) than for the lockdown period (mean 2.18) and for other facilities like incentive package (mean 1.86).

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Do you use mobile banking services in the hope of making more profit?	150	0	5	1.84	1.529
Money deposit in mobile banking services is more profitable.	150	0	5	2.17	1.586
Valid N (listwise)	149				

Source: Field Survey.

This one particular feature is relatively new in M-banking services. When asked the respondents about this issue, they relied on a physical banking system (mean 1.84 and 2.17). This also implies that M-banking still lacks behind traditional banking from this aspect. For significant transactions, safe deposit users still rely on traditional banking. To ensure that E-banking continues to expand, security and privacy must be addressed.

Conclusion

5.1 Findings

The study result shows the influential factors of users' acceptance towards M-banking. Total 35 variables are divided into seven categories based on the conceptual framework. Among them, M-banking is highly influenced by six categories. M-banking services have been operational in Bangladesh for less than ten years. Even everyday MFS services have adopted new features; thus, not all customers are familiar with them.

- The use of banking is much easier on smartphones than bar phones. M-banking application use is also easy, so thus it's all feature.
- Ubiquity has more influence on the use of M-banking. Customers find it time-saving and easy for financial withdrawal.
- M-banking has provided opportunities for its customer to get banking anywhere. It has lessened the suffering of the customers. Now they do not need to go to the bank for the transaction. As discussed in the analysis for (table 5), significant transaction and money deposit customers largely depend on traditional banking. However, ubiquity and banking facilities for all, green services (paperless) are some remarkable facilities of M-banking which attract customers more and more.
- Fraudulent activities are still persistent in mobile banking. In addition, MFSs authorities ensure safety for its customers.
- M-banking multifaceted features allure customers. It is one of the most influential factors which attracts users to m-banking. Bill payment, Top-up, online shopping, discount on financial transaction through the application, money transaction from home and abroad etc., are some special offers where customers feel very effective and time-savings.
- M-banking authorities have slight contact with customers as this system is an agent-based, third-party option where customers can transact money. However, authorities ensure to solve any user problem through customer care services (Online call center and Physical center).
- Mobile banking features are more popular among young age people.
- The results also indicate that respondents like accustomed to using more features rather than just money withdrawal.

Covid-19 pandemic boosted the use of m-banking. When asked whether the covid-19 pandemic has increased the dependency on mobile banking, they expressed it positively.

- Covid-19 incentive package or other economic initiatives of the Government of Bangladesh have nothing to do with the student, jobholder and businessperson.
- M-banking deposit and profit, unlike a bank, customers are not happy with it.

5.2 Practical implication

The study's findings have implications for the deployment of mobile banking systems. Bank clients must adopt mobile banking as a new type of banking. The following suggestions may render ways to attract bank customers to utilize mobile banking more efficiently to achieve this goal.

1. M-banking authority should emphasize the security concern of customer's transaction, agent bankers. Agent banking is a third-party media. BB, MFS, Law enforcement agencies should work collaboratively in this matter to ensure safety.
2. Bangladesh Bank, mobile banking service providers, and law enforcement agencies need to stop fraudulent mobile banking activities. If necessary, the rules should be made stricter.
3. The customer's transaction limit should be removed/made more feasible for the users in mobile banking. They need to find ways to increase the option for significant financial transactions in mobile banking.
4. MFS providers need to reduce the charges on financial transactions. At the same time, MFS has to increase the deposit amount facility such as interest rate and deposit amount limit.
5. Bangladesh has entered the digital age. More opportunities and fields of digital transactions need to be addressed.
6. Mobile banking should be subject to the same regulatory framework as banks.
7. All transactions that affect an account (those that result in an account being debited or credited, including scheduling of such activity) should be permitted only after the mobile number and the PIN linked with it have been authenticated.

Even though computerized innovation such as mobile banking can quicken people's monetary get to create nations like Bangladesh essentially, but did not get appropriate consideration recently COVID-19 widespread. Despite mobile banking begun its travel in 2011 within the nation, its acknowledgment by the customer is prevailing within the later COVID-19 widespread time for getting financial services effectively, expeditiously, and securely. Individuals are presently more cleanly concerned than some time recently. To halt the spread of the COVID-19 widespread, individuals are constrained to open m-banking money accounts on their self-portable gadgets. This brought about a sharp increment within the number of enrolled m-managing account clients amid the widespread circumstance. Diverse m-banking money exchanges such as cash in, cash out, and P2P exchange have strongly expanded amid COVID-19 widespread due to people's changing propensities towards advanced exchanges and diverse government activities. The significance of m-banking has also increased for mobile recharge, settlement exchanges, gift conveyance, security net reserves conveyance, etc. The Government should provide all assistance in establishing a cashless society by providing an easy financial access platform for combating the ongoing pandemic and creating a digital Bangladesh. Even after the COVID-19 epidemic, steps should be taken to increase digital payment systems for social security payments and government employee remuneration.

These measures are intended to assist expedite mobile financial services in Bangladesh during and after the COVID-19 epidemic, eventually increasing people's financial access to a greater level in the following days.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Questionnaire

[Hello! I am Abdus Samad Azad, a Master student of Wuhan University [China] Economics and Management School. As part of my thesis, the opinion of mobile banking users will be taken into account in this study. All personal and institutional information of the participants will be kept confidential; only the provided opinions will be used for quantitative research.

Age	
Occupation	
Monthly Income	

1. Which mobile app do you use? [Notable mobile banking services in Bangladesh are Bkash, Rocket, Nagad, Sure Case, M Cash, U Pay, T Cash, Telecash, etc.]

2. How long have you been using mobile banking services?

Tick (√) in the comments box for the following sentences

SN	Statements	[Strongly Disagree]	[Disagree]	[Somewhat Disagree]	[Somewhat Agree]	[Agree]	[Strongly Agree]
1.	Mobile banking services are much easier to use on bar phones.						
2.	Mobile banking services are much easier to use on smartphones.						
3.	Mobile banking services-related applications are much easier to use.						
4.	Mobile banking services have made my life easier.						
5.	I can use money transactions feature very easily through mobile banking services.						
6.	Mobile banking services allows me to transact money from anywhere.						
7.	The money transactions cost in mobile banking is cheaper.						
8.	For money transactions, I don't need to go to the bank.						
9.	I do large financial transactions in mobile banking services.						
10.	Mobile banking services are much safer.						
11.	I never had been deceived by using mobile banking services.						

12.	In Mobile banking services, there is a risk of fraud.						
13.	I do business transactions through mobile banking services.						
14.	I shop online through mobile banking services.						
15.	I pay electricity bills through mobile banking services.						
16.	I pay gas bills through mobile banking services.						
17.	I pay water bills through mobile banking services.						
18.	I recharge my mobile through mobile banking services.						
19.	Relatives send me money from abroad through mobile banking services.						
20.	Money can be sent abroad through mobile banking services.						
21.	First time I learn about mobile banking services from bank.						
22.	First time I learn about mobile banking services from neighbors'.						
23.	Bank convinces me to use mobile banking services.						
24.	The mobile banking services authority always keeps in touch with me						
25.	I often go to mobile banking service office.						

26.	Covid-19 pandemic have increased the dependency on mobile banking services.						
27.	Do you use mobile banking services in the hope of making more profit?						
28.	Can you easily use mobile banking application?						
29.	The mobile banking application has attractive offers on financial transactions.						
30.	Money deposit in mobile banking services is more profitable.						
31.	Do you use mobile banking services before the outbreak of Covid-19?						
32.	Do you start to use mobile banking services due to the outbreak of Covid-19?						
33.	Do you use mobile banking services due to Covid-19 incentive packages?						
34.	Do you need the help of others to use mobile banking services?						

Thanks for your valuable opinion and time.

Appendix B: Bar charts in Frequency for each statement

Monthly Income Groups

Which mobile banking services do you use? Notable mobile banking services in Bangladesh are Bkash, Rocket, Nagad, Sure Case, M Cash, U Pay, T Cash, Telecash, etc.

Which mobile banking services do you use? Notable mobile banking services in Bangladesh are Bkash, Rocket, Nagad, Sure Case, M Cash, U Pay, T Cash, Telecash, etc.

Mobile banking services are much easier to use on bar phones.

Mobile banking services are much easier to use on bar phones.

Mobile banking services are much easier to use on smartphones.

Mobile banking services are much easier to use on smartphones.

Mobile banking services-related applications are much easier to use.

Mobile banking services-related applications are much easier to use.

Can you easily use mobile banking application?

Can you easily use mobile banking application?

Do you need the help of others to use mobile banking services?

Do you need the help of others to use mobile banking services?

Mobile banking services have made my life easier.

Mobile banking services have made my life easier.

I can use money transactions feature very easily through mobile banking services.

I can use money transactions feature very easily through mobile banking services.

Mobile banking services allows me to transact money from anywhere.

Mobile banking services allows me to transact money from anywhere.

The money transactions cost in mobile banking is cheaper.

The money transactions cost in mobile banking is cheaper.

For money transactions, I don't need to go to the bank.

For money transactions, I don't need to go to the bank.

I do large financial transactions in mobile banking services.

I do large financial transactions in mobile banking services.

I do business transactions through mobile banking services.

I do business transactions through mobile banking services.

Mobile banking services have made my life easier.

Mobile banking services have made my life easier.

I can use money transactions feature very easily through mobile banking services.

I can use money transactions feature very easily through mobile banking services.

Mobile banking services allows me to transact money from anywhere.

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The money transactions cost in mobile banking is cheaper.

The money transactions cost in mobile banking is cheaper.

For money transactions, I don't need to go to the bank.

For money transactions, I don't need to go to the bank.

I do large financial transactions in mobile banking services.

I do large financial transactions in mobile banking services.

I do business transactions through mobile banking services.

I do business transactions through mobile banking services.

I shop online through mobile banking services.

I shop online through mobile banking services.

I pay electricity bills through mobile banking services.

I pay electricity bills through mobile banking services.

I pay gas bills through mobile banking services.

I pay gas bills through mobile banking services.

I pay water bills through mobile banking services.

I pay water bills through mobile banking services.

I recharge my mobile through mobile banking services.

I recharge my mobile through mobile banking services.

Relatives send me money from abroad through mobile banking services.

Relatives send me money from abroad through mobile banking services.

Money can be sent abroad through mobile banking services.

Money can be sent abroad through mobile banking services.

The mobile banking application has attractive offers on financial transactions.

The mobile banking application has attractive offers on financial transactions.

First time I learn about mobile banking services from Bank.

First time I learn about mobile banking services from Bank.

First time I learn about mobile banking services from neighbours.

First time I learn about mobile banking services from neighbours.

Bank convinces me to use mobile banking services.

Bank convinces me to use mobile banking services.

The mobile banking services authority always keeps in touch with me

The mobile banking services authority always keeps in touch with me

I often go to mobile banking service office.

I often go to mobile banking service office.

Covid-19 pandemic have increased the dependency on mobile banking services.

Covid-19 pandemic have increased the dependency on mobile banking services.

Do you use mobile banking services before the outbreak of Covid-19 pandemic?

Do you use mobile banking services before the outbreak of Covid-19 pandemic?

Do you start to use mobile banking services due to the outbreak of Covid-19?

Do you start to use mobile banking services due to the outbreak of Covid-19?

Do you use mobile banking services due to Covid-19 incentive packages?

Do you use mobile banking services due to Covid-19 incentive packages?

Do you use mobile banking services in the hope of making more profit?

Money deposit in mobile banking services is more profitable.

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